

MIXED MODE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS CHARACTERIZATION OF SANDWICH INTERFACES USING THE MODIFIED TSD SPECIMEN

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SUMMARY

An extensive parametric analysis shows that the modified Tilted Sandwich Debond (TSD) specimen provides a methodology for characterization of the face/core fracture resistance over a range of mode-mixities. A pilot experimental mixed mode characterization of the fracture toughness of sandwich specimens, with composite faces and various PVC foam cores spanning a range of phase angles, has been achieved by specific steel bar reinforcements and testing over a range of tilt angles.

Keywords: Face-core interfaces, Debonding/delamination; Mixed mode fracture toughness; Modified TSD specimen, FEA analyses, Experimental characterisation.

INTRODUCTION

A full characterization of debond failure for a sandwich face/core interface requires testing over a wide range of mode-mixities. Only a limited number of test fixtures allow for a direct specification of the mode-mixity applied during the test. A very intriguing test method is the double cantilever beam test with uneven bending moments (DCB-UBM), devised by Sørensen et al. [1] for monolithic composites where the ends of a DCB specimen are loaded by moments. This test was used on sandwich specimens by Østergaard et al. [2] and Lundsgaard-Larsen, et al. [3]. This method produces stable crack growth if run under displacement control since the crack loading does not change with crack length, making the DCB-UBM specimen highly attractive for measurement of interface cohesive laws, where a stable crack growth is required in order to reach a fully developed process zone behind the crack tip. Unfortunately the test method requires a quite complicated test rig and tall test frame, and sandwich specimens also demand ultra-high strength steel reinforcements of the face sheets.

Recently the classic mixed mode bending (MMB) test [4, 5] for monolithic composite specimens was modified for sandwich specimens [6, 7]. Although the sandwich MMB test fixture is less complicated to operate than the DCB-UBM and the specimen does

not need to be reinforced, the range of mode-mixities possible for a fixed specimen geometry, is quite limited.

The Tilted Sandwich Debond (TSD) specimen, shown in Fig. 1, was introduced as a debond test for foam cored sandwich specimens in 1999 by Li and Carlsson [8]. Also this test does not allow much variability of the crack loading.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the conventional TSD specimen.

The characterization of delaminations/debonds in layered materials typically utilizes layered beam specimens with a pre-crack at the interface. Analysis of such specimens has traditionally been focused on a combination of axial loads and pure moments acting on cross sections away from the crack tip region. For shorter crack lengths, however, transverse shear is known to affect the energy release rate of such specimens, and the studies by Li et al. [9] and Ferrie et al. [10] reveal that shear will also change the phase angle, ψ . The shear force will cause rotation of the region close to the crack tip, “root rotation”, in excess of the rotation due to the average transverse shear strain.

Recently a parametric finite element analysis of the TSD specimen [11, 12] showed that by reinforcing the loaded face sheet by a stiff metal plate, an increased transverse shear load leads to increased root rotation of the crack tip resulting in considerable expansion of the range of phase angles. Design considerations furthermore outlined that the range of mode-mixies can be further extended by supporting the core at the cracked end of the specimen. Core crushing at the other end of the specimen due to rotation of the stiff reinforced upper face can be avoided by using pinned links at the right specimen end. Thus, the modified TSD specimen and test was identified as a viable and promising candidate for improved mixed mode fracture toughness measurements [11, 12].

In the present paper the modified TSD specimen will be investigated through an extended numerical parametric study, and experimentally through the testing of a limited pilot series of specimens.

EXTENDED NUMERICAL PARAMETRIC STUDY

In the present study, mode-mixity of the crack is expressed by a phase angle defined as

$$\psi_R = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{K_{II}}{K_I} \right) \quad (1)$$

according to the reduced formulation [12] where K_I and K_{II} are the stress intensity factors in modes I and II, respectively, assuming the oscillatory index, $\varepsilon = 0$. In order to

determine the fracture mechanical properties, i.e. the energy release rate, G , and phase angle, for the various configurations of the modified TSD specimen, a J-integral calculation and the crack surface displacement extrapolation (CSDE) method based on relative crack flank displacements was applied. The CSDE-method was presented earlier by Berggreen [13] in combination with a 2D finite element model similar to the one applied in the present parametric analysis. Expressions for G and ψ_R given in terms of crack flank openings can be found in [12, 13].

Finite element models consisting of 4 and 8 noded iso-parametric plane elements were used in this study. In order to capture the relative crack flank displacements near the tip accurately, Fig. 2, a highly densified mesh was used in the region around the crack tip. Furthermore, the dense mesh region is divided into element rings used for several J-integral calculations. The calculated J-integral values are then averaged and compared with the energy release rate determined from the relative crack flank displacements using the CSDE-method. The finite element mesh is shown in Fig. 2. The modified TSD specimen is shown schematically in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. Finite element mesh used in analysis of the reinforced TSD specimen ($h_s = 12$ mm). (a) global mesh and (b) near tip mesh region. Min. element size is $3.33 \mu\text{m}$.

As mentioned above, a method to increase the range of mode-mixities achievable with the conventional TSD-specimen is to reinforce the upper face sheet with a steel bar, see Fig. 3. The effect of stiffening of the loaded face sheet on the phase angle has earlier been shown in [2] using detailed finite element analysis. Fig. 4a shows the phase angle vs. tilt angle for a varying reinforcement thickness, h_s , and the tilt angle, θ , for a basic sandwich geometry consisting of 2 mm face sheets made from E-glass woven rovings and epoxy resin and 25 mm thick Divinycell H100 foam core [12]. The (steel) reinforcement is considered adhesively bonded to the upper face sheet. Furthermore, in order to maximize the effect of the transverse shear load, a short crack length (25mm) relative to the specimen length is chosen. The geometrical and mechanical properties assumed in the parametric analyses can be found in Tables 1 and 2.

The results in Fig. 4a for the unreinforced original TSD specimen with a H100 core ($h_s = 0$) show that, the phase angle is almost constant over the range of tilt angles between $\{-75^\circ < \theta < 75^\circ\}$, confirming the findings by Li and Carlsson [2]. However, Fig. 4a shows also that by reinforcing the upper face sheet with a stiff steel layer the range of phase angles is expanded. With a reinforcement thickness of 12 mm the variability of the phase angle range for the H100 core is increased to about $\psi_R = -70^\circ$ for $\theta = 85^\circ$ and $\psi_R = 70^\circ$ for $\theta = -85^\circ$. Similar results can be seen for the H45 and H200 cases, see [12].

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the modified *plain* TSD specimen.

Table 1: Geometrical properties in the parametric analysis.

Geometrical Properties		
Specimen length (mm)	L	200
Face thickness (mm)	h_f	2, 4
Core thickness (mm)	h_c	5, 10, 25, 50, 100
Crack length (mm)	a	25, 50
Reinforcement thicknesses (mm)	h_s	1, 2, 4, 8, 12
Tilt angle (°)	θ	-85, -75, -60, -30, 0, 30, 60, 75, 85

Table 2: Mechanical properties of face, core and steel.

Mechanical Properties					
Face (GFRP, CFRP)			Cores (H45, H100, H200)		
In-plane Young's moduli (GPa)	E_1	20.6	Young's modulus (MPa)	E_c	55
	E_2	44.0			130
Out-of-plane Young's modulus (GPa)	E_3	9.90	Shear modulus (MPa)	G_c	15
		9.90			35
					85
In-plane shear modulus (GPa)	G_{12}	3.10	Poisson's ratio (-)	ν_c	0.32
		6.62			0.32
		0.32			
Out-of-plane shear moduli (GPa)	G_{13}	2.90	Steel Reinforcement		
	G_{23}	6.20			
In-plane Poisson's ratio (-)	ν_{12}	0.12	Young's modulus (GPa)	E_s	210
Out-of-plane Poisson's ratios (-)	ν_{13}	0.37	Poisson's ratio (-)	ν_s	0.3
	ν_{23}	0.37			

To investigate the response and mechanical behavior of the modified TSD-specimen when changing the crack length as well as the mechanical properties of the face and core, respectively, a series of parametric analyses have been carried out as presented below.

Effect of Crack Length

Fig. 4b shows the phase angle as function of tilt angle for a steel reinforced ($h_s = 12$ mm) GFRP/H100 TSD specimen with a 2 mm thick face sheet and 25 mm thick H100 core for crack lengths of 25 to 150 mm. As the crack length increases the relative shear contribution diminishes. Hence, the crack loading becomes more mode I dominated at longer crack lengths.

Figure 4. Phase angle as function of tilt angle for reinforced H100 TSD specimen (left). The influence of crack length on the phase angle (reduced formulation) as function of positive tilt angles (right) for a reinforced ($h_s = 12 \text{ mm}$) GFRP/H100 TSD specimen with 2 mm face and 25 mm core thickness.

Effect of Face Sheets

Face sheet thicknesses of 2 and 4 mm were considered. Fig. 5a shows the phase angle as a function of the tilt angle for TSD specimens with the two face thicknesses. A 12 mm thick steel reinforcement and a H100 core were considered. It can be observed that the face thickness has a small influence on the phase angle. This is expected since the 12 mm thick steel reinforcement will dominate the structural response of the specimen. Thus, it can be concluded that for the TSD specimen reinforced with a thick steel reinforcement, precise determination of face sheet thicknesses is not important.

The influence of face material selection on the phase angle is investigated for a TSD specimen with a 12 mm thick steel reinforcement and H100 core. The crack length was 25 mm and the face and core were 2 and 25 mm, respectively. Typical material properties for GFRP and CFRP face sheets, see Table 2, were assumed. The results shown in Fig. 5b verify that the face modulus has virtually no influence on the phase angle. It can be concluded as well that a precise measurement of the face sheet stiffness is not necessary for the modified TSD-specimen.

Figure 5. The influence of face thickness (left) and typical face material selections (right) on the phase angle as function of tilt angle for a reinforced ($h_s = 12 \text{ mm}$) H100 TSD specimen with 25 mm crack length and 25 mm core thickness.

Fig. 6a shows the influence of tilt angle on the load required to achieve $G = G_{Ic}$ for a specimen with ($h_s = 12 \text{ mm}$) with a H100 core with a 25 mm crack, 2 mm thick face and 25 mm thick core. Both CFRP and GFRP faces (properties in Table 2) were examined. It can be observed that the applied load is increasing rapidly for higher tilt and thus phase angles, associated with a higher degree of mode II loading and decreasing compliance of the specimen. This must be considered when testing reinforced TSD specimens at high tilt angles. Again it can be concluded from the results that the face sheet stiffness has no effect on the load level.

Figure 6. Load required to achieve $G = G_{Ic}$ as function of tilt angle (left) and phase angle vs. tilt angle for core thicknesses from 5 to 100 mm (right) for a reinforced ($h_s = 12 \text{ mm}$) H100 TSD specimen with 25 mm crack length and 2 mm face.

Effect of Core

H100 core thicknesses in the range from 5 to 100 mm were examined. The steel reinforcement was 12 mm thick, the face 2 mm thick and the crack length 25 mm. Fig. 6b shows that the phase angle at a given tilt angle increases with decreasing core thickness. A reduced core thickness will increase the concentration of localized shear deformation at the crack tip, thus resulting in more crack tip rotation.

The influence of core density on the phase angle (reduced formulation) was examined for a TSD specimen with a 12 mm steel reinforcement. The face and core thicknesses were 2 and 25 mm, and the crack length 25 mm. Fig. 7a shows that the core density does not appreciably influence the phase angle. Fig. 7b shows the influence of core density on the load required to achieve $G = G_{Ic}$. The required load is highly affected by the core density and increases with increasing core density.

Further Design Modifications

As shown above in Fig. 4a and 6b the reinforcement and core thicknesses have a large influence on the phase angle. To localize shear deformation of the core, a reinforcement of the left edge of the TSD specimen could become effective. To simulate such a reinforcement, the DOF's at all nodes on the left edge of the specimen were fixed for a H100 specimens with 25 mm thick core and 2 mm thick face sheets with a 12 mm steel

reinforcement. Fig. 8a shows that such a reinforcement is effective for tilt angles between $\{20^\circ < \theta < 85^\circ\}$ where the variability of the phase angle increases. Moreover, the results in Fig. 8b, show that both the shape and magnitude of the phase angle vs. tilt angle relationship collapses into a more uniform relation, when changing the core thickness. This is quite different than the results for TSD specimens without the end block shown in Fig. 6b. Thus shear deformation are more localized at the crack tip region with larger crack tip rotations as a result. For core thicknesses less than 10 mm it is further observed from Fig. 6b that the phase angle vs. tilt angle relationship deviates from the general trend achieved for larger core thicknesses. It is believed that this behavior is due to the influence of the lower face sheet on the local crack tip deformation field. It can be concluded that a reinforcement of the left core edge seems attractive in order to achieve a higher degree of phase angle variability.

Figure 7. Phase angle vs. tilt angle for three core densities (left) and the influence of core density on the load required to achieve $G = G_{Ic}$ (core) as function of tilt angle (right) for face reinforced TSD specimens ($h_s = 12$ mm) with 25 mm crack length, 2 mm face and 25 mm core thicknesses.

Figure 8. The influence of core end reinforcement (End Block) for $h_c = 25$ mm (left) and core thickness (right) on the phase angle as function of tilt angle for a reinforced ($h_s = 12$ mm) GFRP/H100 TSD specimen with 25 mm crack length and 2 mm face thickness.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Fracture Testing

Experimental investigation of the modified TSD specimen has been carried out on specimens with H60 core and E-glass/epoxy face sheets with lay-up configuration $[0/90]_4$. The mechanical properties of the core were measured, whereas the face properties were estimated using classical lamination theory. All mechanical properties can be found in Table 3.

In addition to the steel bar and end block reinforcements discussed above, it was pointed out in [11, 12] that in order to avoid crushing of the right core end of the specimen, rigid pinned links should be attached between the face sheet reinforcement and base of the test rig, see Fig. 9. All design modifications were adopted in the present experimental investigation. An initial crack of length of 35 mm was cut into all specimens. In order to measure a realistic fracture toughness similar to what would be encountered in a debond damaged sandwich structure, the crack tip was sharpened by propagating the crack slightly prior to the attachment of the steel reinforcement. Five specimens were tested in a TSD rig mounted in a 20 kN electro-mechanical testing machine, see Fig. 9. Quasi-static loading of 2 mm/min were applied in displacement control. The test program is summarized in Table 4.

Figure 9. Further design modifications with pinned links at both sides of the specimen and an additional block, supporting the left end of the TSD specimen.

Table 3: Mechanical properties for test specimens of face, core and steel.

Mechanical Properties					
Face (GFRP $[0, 90]_4$)			Core (H60)		
In-plane Young's moduli (GPa)	E_1, E_2	23.6	Young's modulus (MPa)	E_c	41.5
Out-of-plane Young's modulus (GPa)	E_3	9.90	Shear modulus (MPa)	G_c	15.7
In-plane shear modulus (GPa)	G_{12}	5.00	Poisson's ratio (-)	ν_c	0.32
Out-of-plane shear moduli (GPa)	G_{13}, G_{23}	3.00	Steel Reinforcement		
In-plane Poisson's ratio (-)	ν_{12}	0.08	Young's modulus (GPa)	E_s	210
Out-of-plane Poisson's ratios (-)	ν_{13}, ν_{23}	0.37	Poisson's ratio (-)	ν_s	0.3

Table 4: Test matrix.

Geometrical Properties		
Specimen length (mm)	L	200
Face thickness (mm)	h_f	4
Core thickness (mm)	h_c	24
Crack length (mm)	a	35
Reinforcement thicknesses (mm)	h_s	12
Tilt angle (°)	θ	15, 30, 44, 60, 69

Table 5: Propagation loads.

Propagation loads		
Test	θ [°]	P_{prop} [kN]
1	15	0.70
2	30	0.81
3	44	1.07
4	60	1.50
5	69	2.50

In all five tests unstable crack propagation was observed. Due to the unstable crack propagation only one measurement for each specimen was possible. Furthermore, for the specimens tested with a tilt angle of 15° and 30°, the crack kinked out of the interface and into the core at an angle of 3° and 6°, respectively. For the remaining specimens the crack propagated just below the resin rich area on the core side of the face/core interface. The crack paths for all 5 specimens can be seen in Fig. 10.

Figure 10. Crack paths from right to left at various tilt angles. 15° (#4), 30° (#3), 44° (#5), 60° (#1) and 69° (#2).

In order to relate the tested tilt angles with a correlating phase angle, and to calculate the critical energy release rate at propagation (the fracture toughness), finite element analyses were conducted using the same model as described earlier. In addition to the tested tilt angles, a not tested tilt angle of 80° was included in the analysis in order to determine the phase angle at very high tilt angles. Fig. 11 shows the phase angle vs. tilt angle and fracture toughness vs. phase angle respectively.

Discussion

As shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 in connection with the parametric study above, neither an accurate determination of face sheet thickness or material parameters are important for the accurate determination of the phase angle applied for a chosen tilt angle. Thus, it is concluded that the estimated face sheet properties adopted in the calculation of the phase angles presented in Fig. 11a do not affect the accuracy significantly.

For low tilt angles it was observed that the crack kinked slightly into the core, which is in good agreement with the general crack kinking mechanism for positive mixed mode phase angles. However, in order to determine the transition phase angle between continued interface crack propagation and crack kinking into the core, a more detailed crack kinking analysis must be carried out as presented in either [13] or [14].

Figure 11. Calculated phase angle vs. tilt angle for tested and not tested specimens (left). Fracture toughness vs. phase angle for tested specimens (right).

Fig. 11b shows the measured fracture toughness over a range of phase angles tested. The magnitude of the fracture toughness is in good agreement with earlier measured fracture toughness values for similar material configurations [7, 13]. An increasing tendency for decreasing phase angles can be observed due to increased shear loading at the crack tip. However, as reported for earlier fracture toughness measurements in foam core sandwich specimens, significant scatter can be expected. Accordingly, the results presented here should be taken with reservation, and it is recommended that additional tests should be carried out.

CONCLUSIONS

Design modifications of the TSD specimen have been examined, and it was shown through an expanded parametric investigation that the accuracy of the specimen face sheet properties and core density does not change the phase angle significantly. However, adoption of a specific face and core reinforcements combined with a pinned core end link-reinforcement increases the phase angle variability considerably. A limited experimental investigation was carried out on sandwich specimens with the adopted reinforcements over a range of phase angles, and the observed crack paths and measured fracture toughnesses were in general agreement with the literature. However, further experimental measurements should be carried out to fully investigate the behaviour and performance of the modified TSD specimen.

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